

Metaphysical Healing – New Thought or Old?

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We hear a lot about New Thought, and people use this term interchangeable with Metaphysical practices, being positive. But is it really NEW or are we just recycling thoughts and updating the terminology?

The Science of Mind magazine that was 1st published in 1927 by Ernest Holmes brought new thought into the main stream. I say this as instead of having to go to a meeting and being branded as having bazaar thoughts of creation and life. People were free to explore this information in the privacy of their home without judgment from anyone who saw them attending such an outlandish meeting.

In his book “The Science of Mind, in the chapter titled ANOTHER GREAT DISCOVERY—THOUGHT REACHED OTHERS it was stated, “he could think of them and heal them.” Many credit him with being “THE” New Thought teacher.

However, Mary Baker Eddy who registered the "Science and Health" program in 1875 was already teaching the Principle of scientific mental healing and that physical illness can be corrected by prayer in a positive atmosphere and that this information was something we had but lost with all the religious dogma through the ages. She gave all credit to the Divine Mind of God within us and not to our own power (paraphrased from “Science and Mind” with keys to the Scriptures by Mary Baker Eddy Chapter 6 Science, Theology, Medicine page 110 v.15-27 (The demonstration lost and found).

With this we have the basis of Metaphysical Healing and positive thought as currently taught by Dr. Paul Leon Masters in his course “Master’s Degree Course Study Modules vol. 2, The Practitioner’s Metaphysical Healing Practice. Meditating daily and connecting with your inner God Spirit should be the first step in awakening that healing within that helps you to be able to heal others. One thing they all stress is to heal yourself first. Take the beam out of your

own eye before you try to take the splinter out of your brother or sister.

Since we are electrical energy in our inherent nature, with metaphysics we learn to understand we have the ability to send this energy to others. This flow of energy that comes from the Divine into our body and out again, mirrors the eastern practice of Reiki.

Reiki is the eastern healing modality that teaches hands on healing method by sending your energy to someone by thought or hands on. The energy will then go to the area where the healing is most needed.

With Metaphysical healing treatments work much the same way, however the energy you are sending is made in a meditative state of oneness with the Universal God Mind, so the energy is not just your thought energy but the energy that is flowing from the Oneness Source through you to the other individual seeking healing. Again, this can be done long distance or in person. Where Reiki can be hands on Metaphysical methods can be more of holding your hands above the body and not touching it combined with meditation and affirmations.

So how old is this teaching of healing with the Universal Mind Energy? Much before 1875 When Mary Baker Eddy set down the exact steps of being one with the God within to heal. Jesus would meditate alone daily or pray and then he went and healed, but the practice goes way back before him. All religions on earth have some form of energy healing that is done and was passed down from the Angelic Messenger to Shaman to student.

Metaphysics or New Thought is not new. We are being now made aware of the collective energy that has always been there, but we were too concerned with other things to want to connect with our Divine energy, our Spirit Guides, our Angelic Guides who come straight from the center of our creator. They bring peace, knowledge and yes prosperity. How can we

spread the good news that God is within and we create our own heaven on earth unless we have the means to do so?

All through the ages we have been being guided towards this time in our collective history. We are calling it New Thought, but it's been around since the beginning of time.

When the Pagans celebrated the first Summer solstice, they were giving thanks for being one with nature and using Nature to heal. When the Christians started celebrating Easter they were giving thanks for renewal and rebirth. During this time the Hindus were celebrating *Holi* or *Phagwah* a popular spring festival. Holi commemorates the slaying of the demoness Holika by Lord Vishnu's devotee Prahlad. Out with the bad, in with the good. You will find spring time celebrations in all religions and most relate to being healed and given a new body. We are all one and we all celebrate the good.

It's not new it's always been there, waiting for us to catch up, wake up and become aware that you are in charge of this earthly experiment. What you think and say has a direct reaction on your life and those around you. The information has always been in you, now turn the page and read what you already know as truth. Be kind to one another and help one another. Think positive in all things and all things positive will come to you. This is the law of attraction, the universal law of love, the golden rule.

We may call it New Thought and I look at it this way. The light bulb came on and it seems like a new thought to us, but we have known about it for a very long time. It was just buried very deep with us. Now we have the time to actually ask the question of how this can be done and receive the answers that are already here. New Thought? No, not really. Forgotten Thought would be more like it. We who study the Way of The Magi want to help the world remember the oneness that was forgotten.

About Joy Maestas

J. Joy Maestas, known as Rev. Joy, is an ordained metaphysical minister with the International Metaphysical Ministry. She received her Master of Metaphysical Science from the University of Metaphysics in Sedona, Arizona. She is currently working toward her Doctorate. Rev. Joy founded Universal Light Ministries in Tucson to help others live positively and find the Universal Divine Love within themselves and has written numerous books on metaphysics.